

Synthesis and Swelling behavior of Poly(N-tert-amylacrylamide -co -acrylamide / AMPS Na) Nanocomposite Hydrogels

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Abstract

A series of ionic poly(N-tert-amylacrylamide -co -acrylamide / AMPS Na) nanocomposite Hydrogels were synthesized by free-radical copolymerization in Water/Methanol medium using Ammonium persulfate (APS) as the initiator and N,N-methylenebisacrylamide (MBA) as a crosslinker at 60°C. The Nanocomposites Hydrogels were prepared via in situ polymerization using Organo modified MMT(O-MMT) Nano clay. The amount of N-tert-amylacrylamide (NTA) and Acrylamide (AM) monomers was fixed and the amount of AMPS Na acid was varied. The Hydrogels were characterized by IR spectroscopy. The swelling behavior of Nanocomposite Hydrogels studied by Gravimetric method and degree of swelling was increased by increasing the amount of AMPS Na. The surface morphology was studied by SEM analysis.

Keywords : Hydrogels, N-tert-amylacrylamide , Swelling behavior , SEM analysis

1. Introduction

Hydrogels are three-dimensional crosslinked hydrophilic polymer networks, which swell without dissolving when brought into water or biological fluids [1]. These crosslinked polymers have been used widely in various types of applications such as controlled drug delivery, immobilization of enzymes, dewatering of protein solution, solute separation, baby diapers, soil for agriculture and horticulture, water-blocking tape, absorbent pads, and others [2-4].

Hydrogels can swell to profitable rates when placed into an appropriate environment, which means a specific pH, temperature, electric field, light, pressure or specific molecule [5-11]. Several researchers have studied the swelling of pH-sensitive hydrogels and the influence of this parameter in chemical, biological and physiological systems [12]. Hydrogels exhibiting pH-sensitive swelling behavior have been usually swollen from ionic networks that can contain acidic or basic pendant groups. When these groups are ionized, a swelling osmotic pressure inside the material is built up, and fixed charges are trapped in the gel. As a result of the electrostatic repulsion, the uptake of solvent in the network is increased [13-16].

These observations inspired us to synthesize the hydrogels based on N-tert-amylacrylamide (NTA). The aim of this work was to prepare a series of poly(N-tert-amylacrylamide -co -acrylamide / AMPSNa) Nanocomposite Hydrogels, based on NTA, acrylamide and AMPSNa. Synthesis and swelling behavior of such copolymer gels have not been reported before. Hydrogels were prepared by free-radical crosslinking copolymerization of NTA, AM and AMPSNa in the presence of N,N'-methylenebis(acrylamide) (MBA) as the crosslinker.

Experimental

Preparation of N-tert-amylacrylamide (NTA)

The monomer N-tert-amylacrylamide was prepared by the reaction of t-amyl alcohol with acrylonitrile. N-tert-amylacrylamide was recrystallized in warm dry benzene. The white crystals have a m.p. 91°C (Lit. $91-92^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the yield was $\sim 87\%$.

$^1\text{H-NMR}(\text{CDCl}_3), \delta(\text{ppm}) :$

At 0.78 ppm for $-\text{CH}_3$, at 1.2 ppm for $-(\text{CH}_2)_2$, at 1.7 ppm for $-\text{CH}_2$, at 5.49 ppm for $=\text{CH}$ vinyl proton and at 6.1 ppm for vinyl $=\text{CH}_2$ proton

Preparation of Hydrogels

Free-radical crosslinking copolymerization was carried out in methanol /water mixture as the polymerization solvent, at 60°C in the presence of APS as initiator and MBA as crosslinker. Aqueous solution containing NTA (0.5g), AM (0.5g), 0.045g MBA, 0.005 g APS, AMPS Na (0.10, 0.20, 0.30 g and 0.4g) were prepared in methanol water mixture. The amount of O-MMT clay was varied from 50mg to 150 mg. The clay was added with stirring. After bubbling nitrogen for 15 min, the contents were placed in thermostatic water bath at 60°C and the polymerization was conducted for 1 day (Scheme-1). After the reaction, the hydrogels were cut into pieces 3-4 mm long. The extracted hydrogels were dried in vacuum oven at 50°C to constant weight for further use.

Swelling characteristics

The swelling characteristics were measured by immersing weighed samples of dry hydrogels in double distilled water. The excess surface water in the swollen gel was removed by blotting and then the swollen gel was weighed. The degree of swelling (Ds) most commonly described as swelling ratio is expressed as increase in weight / gm of dried hydrogel after keeping in contact with water for selected period of time.

$$\text{Degree of swelling (Ds)} = \frac{(W_s - W_d)}{W_d} \quad (1)$$

Where, W_s is the weight of the swollen gel at a given time and W_d is the weight of the dry gel. The equilibrium water content (EWC) is expressed in % on the weight of swollen gel at equilibrium, using the Eqn.2. Where, W_e is the weight of the swollen gel at equilibrium and W_d is the weight of the dry gel.

$$\text{EWC} = \frac{(W_e - W_d)}{W_e} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The swelling experiments were carried out as a function of time and the negligible change in weight of swollen gel is taken to be indicative of the equilibrium stage.

SEM Analysis

The Micro structure of Hydrogels were studied by Scanning electron Microscopy hydrogels were performed using Hitach, model-JSM-5000 imaging mode at 30 kV with varying levels of magnification

Results and discussion

The ¹H-NMR data of N-tert-amylacrylamide: at 0.78ppm for-CH₃ , at 1.2ppm for-(CH₃)₂, at 1.7 ppm for- CH₂, at5.49 ppm for =CH vinyl proton and at 6.1ppm for vinyl =CH₂ proton .

IR Spectral characterization of Hydrogel

The IR analysis of the hydrogels showed that the presence of peaks corresponding to the functional groups of monomeric units present in the copolymeric hydrogel chain .A broad peak corresponding to NH of AMPS Na as well as NH stretching of acrylamide was observed around 3432 cm⁻¹ . In addition to this, the peaks were also observed at 1634 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O of NTA unit and 1535 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=ONH₂ AM unit. The peak observed at 1449 cm⁻¹ corresponding to S=O (Sym) .

The schematic representation of the Hydrogel is shown below

Scheme 1: Poly (NTA-co- AM/ AMPS Na) Nanocomposite Hydrogel

Swelling Behavior

Dynamic swelling of some selected samples at different absorbing time in water was measured as shown in Figure 1. The swelling rate was slow during the first few minutes, it indicates that the initial swelling is due primarily to the water penetrating into the polymeric gel through capillary and diffusion. Then the penetrated water is absorbed by hydrophilic groups such as AMPS Na and AM through formation of hydrogen bonds. The swelling is driven by repulsion of hydrophilic groups inside the network and osmotic pressure difference between the gels and the external solution. The swelling rate is gradually increases until the equilibrium swelling is reached. The swelling rate observed for AMPS Na 0.1 g to 0.40 g. As the content of AMPS Na is increases the swelling rate is increases rapidly. The incorporation of hydrophilic groups AMPS Na favorable to penetration of water.

Figure 1:Swelling behavior of Nanocomposite Hydrogels(▲ : 0.1g ; ◆:0.2g ; ■:0.3g ;X:0.4g of AMPSNa)

Surface Morphology

The Surface Morphology of Nanocomposite studied by SEM analysis. The SEM image of the nanocomposite Hydrogel was shown in Figure 2. The image indicates the presence of nanocomposite as nano rod shape. These nano rods were distributed uniformly throughout the polymer matrix.

Figure 2: SEM image of Poly (NTA-co- AM/ AMPS Na) Nanocomposite Hydrogel

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